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DATA HIDING SCHEME BASED ON PIXEL VALUE DIFFERENCING IN DUAL IMAGES

¹Arunkumar K G, ²Mr A Jasmine Antony Raj

¹PG Student, ²Assistant Professor,

^{1,2}Department of Information Technology,

^{1,2}Hindusthan College of Arts and Science (Autonomous),

^{1,2}Coimbatore, TamilNadu, India.

ABSTRACT - Data hiding is to conceal the mysterious message in to cover objects without distortion. In the proposed method, another data hiding technique is proposed to provide high embedding limit in dual images. The proposed strategy produces two ego images after embedding the mysterious pieces into a cover picture. A sub square of two consecutive pixels is utilized to have different length of embedding pieces by applying the difference value of two pixels. The experimental results show that the proposed technique can have a high embedding limit maintaining less distortion.

Keywords - [Data hiding, objects, dual images, pixels.]

1. INTRODUCTION

It is vital issue the data framework needs to give the security as duplicate and spread of interactive media data is excessively simple by the Internet. In security data frameworks, cryptography and data hiding strategies are two significant fields to beat copyright and possession issues. Cryptography is going to secure the substance of restricted information, though data hiding is to conceal the presence of privileged information [1]. Data hiding strategies can be separated into reversible and irreversible data hiding techniques whether the cover object which is utilized in installing privileged information can be recuperated or not [2]–[9]. In irreversible data hiding strategies, the most un-critical pieces substitution and pixel-esteem differencing methods are by and large utilized. The substitution technique substitutes the most un-huge pieces with the inserting pieces. The strategy utilizes the distinction worth of two sequential non-covering pixels. In this paper, another data hiding technique utilizing pixel-esteem differencing in dual images is proposed to give high implanting limit.

2. EXISTING SYSTEM:

- ❖ Using the congruity of pixels to change the square size and change the compass mode can update picture embedded cutoff.
- ❖ The various layer installing method is changed rendition proposed by Alattar by changing the quad stages for recursive inserting to nine changes

3. DISADVANTAGES OF EXISTING SYSTEM:

- ❖ Having pixel twisting from message covering.
- ❖ Multi-Pixel Difference Expansion is inconvenient connection.

- ❖ Improvement of introduced limit is relied upon to cover huge data.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM:

- ❖ Key based encryption is performed.
- ❖ In data hiding, two covering continuous pixels are acclimated with implanting favored data.
- ❖ Two pixel pair are used to make dual stego images
- ❖ In extraction, the favored data can be acquired by dual stego images.
- ❖ Difference of not really set in stone
- ❖ The secretive pieces can be finished up by referring to the lower bound in the arrive at table.

5. ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM:

- ❖ Provide high installing limit
- ❖ Supports versatile extensibility
- ❖ Less bending

6. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE:

CONCLUSION

In this endeavor another data hiding plan utilizing pixel-esteem differencing in dual images has been proposed. The proposed technique utilized the pixel-esteem differencing estimation in dual images and two successive pixels are covered to give high inserting limit. The exploratory results exhibited that the proposed strategy was incredible to the histogram attack. The exploratory results similarly showed that the proposed plan could embed 845,922 pieces and kept up with 38.78 dB and 38.68 Db taking everything into

account. Later on, the proposed procedure will be improved to give the reversibility.

REFERENCES

- [1]. A. Cheddad, J. Condell, K. Curran, and P. Kevitt, "Digital Image Steganography: Survey and Analysis of Current Methods", *Signal Process*, Elsevier, pp. 727-752, March 2010.
- [2]. D. Wu and W. Tsai, "A Steganographic Method for Images by Pixel-Value Differencing", *Pattern Recognition Letters*, Elsevier, pp. 1613-1626, June 2003.
- [3]. K. Jung, "A Survey of Reversible Data Hiding Methods in Dual Images", *IETE Technical Review*, Taylor & Francis, pp. 441-452, April 2016.
- [4]. T. Lu, C. Tseng, and J. Wu, "Dual Image-Based Reversible Hiding Technique Using LSB Matching", *Signal Processing*, ACM Digital Library, pp. 77-89, March 2015.
- [5]. C. Qin, C. Chang, and T. Hsu, "Reversible Data Hiding Scheme Based on Exploiting Modification Direction with Two Steganographic Images", *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, Springer, pp. 5861-5872, August 2015.
- [6]. K. Jung and K. Yoo, "Steganographic Method Based on Interpolation and LSB Substitution of Digital Images", *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, Springer, pp. 2143-2155, March 2015.
- [7]. H. Huang and F. Chang, "Hierarchy-Based Reversible Data Hiding", *Experts Systems with Applications*, Elsevier, pp. 34-43, January 2013.
- [8]. Y. Chen, C. Shiu, and G. Horng, "Encrypted Signal-Based Reversible Data Hiding with Public Key Cryptosystem", *Journal of Visual Communication and Image Representation*, Elsevier, pp. 1164-1170, July 2014.